

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART VI.

N¹-AND N⁴-SUBSTITUTED SULPHANILAMIDES : N⁴-SULPHONYL
DERIVATIVES OF SULPHAPYRIDINE AND SULPHATHIAZOLE

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Ten aromatic sulphonyl derivatives of sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine have been prepared.

Special interest attaches to sulphanilamide (A) and to the related group of sulphonyl derivatives.

The therapeutic effect of (A) reported simultaneously by a number of investigators. (Fourneau and co-workers, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1936, 122, 258) studied the therapeutic effect of N⁴-(acetylsulphanilyl-) sulphanilamide,

and reported as having only very little potency.

Further work along this line was continued by Crossley and Northey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2222) who synthesised the sulphanilyl derivatives of a number of N¹-substituted sulphanilamides. They found that the addition of a sulphanilyl group to the amino group increased the activity still further. However, a good contrast was afforded by N³-sulphanilyl metanilamide

which was found to be more active than N⁴-metanilyl sulphanilamide

the first compound behaving as N¹-metanilamide substituted sulphanilamide, while the second as N⁴-metanilamide substituted sulphanilamide.

Sprague, McBurney and Kissinger (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1714) extended this work further by preparing a few N^4 -sulphonyl derivatives, other than sulphanilyl with some alkyl sulphonic acids. They found that the introduction of a sulphonyl group into the N^4 position of the sulphanilamide molecule markedly reduced the activity, the toxicity getting reduced at the same time as compared with that of sulphanilamide.

Thus in general it is found that the introduction of a sulphonyl group at N^4 position reduces the activity, except in the case of N^4 -sulphanilyl derivatives which may be looked upon as N^1 -substituted sulphanilamides with the free amino group in the *p*-position. The toxic effect of these sulphonyl derivatives is, however, very much lower than that of the parent compound. Further, though a few such derivatives of sulphanilamide itself have been prepared, similar derivatives of the two famous drugs, *viz.*, of sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine have not been prepared so far. These considerations led us to synthesise a few aryl sulphonyl derivatives of sulphapyridine and sulphathiazole, which are listed in the table. Among these derivatives sulphanilyl sulphathiazole (I) and sulphanilyl sulphapyridine (II) are of special significance as they are expected to possess good therapeutic activity.

The preparation of these derivatives was effected by the action of the respective sulphonyl chlorides on sulphapyridine or sulphathiazole in aqueous alkaline solution as detailed in the experimental part. The respective benzene and toluene sulphonyl chlorides were prepared by the action of chlorosulphonic acid on benzene and toluene. The sulphanilyl derivatives were prepared by reacting *p*-acetylsulphanilyl chloride on sulphathiazole or sulphapyridine, followed by hydrolysis of the acetylsulphanilyl derivative.

The compounds were purified by crystallisation from alcohol. They are all colourless amorphous compounds with sharp melting points and sparing solubility in water. The pharmacological examination is awaited.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The compounds prepared are described in the Table I.

TABLE I.

Sulphathiazole derivative

Sulphapyridine derivative

R	Name of sulphonic acid used.	Sulphonyl derivatives of sulphathiazole.			Sulphonyl derivatives of sulphapyridine.		
		M.p.	Nitrogen		M.p.	Nitrogen	
			Found.	Theo.		Found.	Theo.
C_6H_5	Benzene	189°	10.13%	10.63%	230°	10.67%	10.88%
$CH_3.C_6H_4-$	<i>p</i> -Toluene	172°	10.92	10.27	160°	10.73	10.42
<i>p</i> - $CH_3CONH.C_6H_4-$	<i>p</i> -Acetaminobenzene	128-30°	12.92	12.39	115-46°	12.34	12.30
<i>p</i> - $NH_2.C_6H_4-$	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzene	210°	13.62	13.65	236°-38°	13.35	13.90
<i>m</i> - $NO_2.C_6H_4-$	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzene	175°	12.54	12.69	185°	11.86	12.90

The benzene, toluene, *p*-acetaminobenzene and *m*-nitrobenzene sulphonyl derivatives were prepared by the following general procedure.

Preparation of Benzenesulphonyl sulphathiazole.—Sulphathiazole (1g.) was suspended in water and to the mixture gradually added drop by drop 2 c.c. of benzene sulphonyl chloride (freshly distilled) with good shaking. After each addition of the sulphonyl chloride a few drops of 10% sodium hydroxide were added with good shaking, maintaining the solution feebly alkaline throughout.

After the addition was over, the product was allowed to stand with occasional shaking for 2 hours, and the separated solid was filtered off, washed with water and alcohol, dried and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 189°, yield 1.2g.

The sulphanilyl derivatives were prepared by hydrolysis of the corresponding acetsulphanilyl derivatives with 10% hydrochloric acid as usual.